

doi 10.5281/zenodo.8147219

Vol. 06 Issue 07 July - 2023

Manuscript ID: #0912

REVIEW OF RECRUITMENT PROCEDURES AND CONTRACT EMPLOYEE SELECTION IN SAMARINDA STATE POLYTECHNIC

Maskan, Marsuq, Jamiah, Muhammad Ikhsan Sidiq

Faculty of Social Sciences and Political Science, University of 17 Agustus 1945 Samarinda

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the procedures for recruiting and selecting contract employees at the Samarinda State Polytechnic. This descriptive qualitative research was conducted from February to May 2023 at the Samarinda State Polytechnic Campus. Data collection techniques through interviews, observation, and literature study. Qualitative data analysis includes data collection, reduction, presentation, and conclusion. The results of the study show that: (1) In carrying out the recruitment procedures at the Samarinda State Polytechnic, it already has a basis as a reference, namely the director's regulations, which contain specifications, implementation procedures, and systematic recruitment; (2) two sources of recruitment are used, namely Internal and External, (3) The recruitment method uses the open method, (4) for preliminary acceptance, a selection of files is carried out by the Selection Committee (Selection Committee) specially made by the personnel sector, (5) tests The selection carried out is a preliminary test or file selection, then there are academic tests and physical or health tests for certain fields only, and (6) selection interviews are carried out by people who are competent in exploring information, potential, and motivation of prospective contract employees in work to be the assessment and evaluation material of the selection committee.

KEYWORDS

Recruitment Procedures, Contract Employees, Samarinda State Polytechnic

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

INTRODUCTION

Human Resources is very influential on the progress of a company, organization, and agency. Without human resources working in an agency, the agency cannot operate properly. An agency's progress caused by employees is to see how much ability the employee has in advancing an agency. Employee relations with agencies are two mutually beneficial things. Advanced agencies will provide welfare for their employees, and an agency to progress and develop requires employees who can work according to the agency's expectations.

Agency employees are defined as assets or investments owned by agencies, so an agency must be careful in choosing employees. This is where the role of recruitment is the first step in selecting prospective employees in agencies. Recruitment is very influential on employees owned by agencies because recruitment is the process of gathering and looking for prospective workers by notifying the public that agencies need prospective workers to be placed in certain positions through certain selection according to the criteria set by the company.

The main objective of an agency or organization carrying out recruitment and selection is to find and determine employees who fit the agency's criteria so they can later bring progress to the agency. While the aim of agencies looking for quality employees is as a resource owned by agencies to be later able to provide change for agencies because quality employees will also increase the quality of an institution.

The implementation of recruitment and selection is based on the correct and appropriate method to achieve the "Right man in the right place" by placing someone according to their abilities or expertise. The method is the most appropriate and efficient to get employees according to the agency's needs. Recruitment methods as revealed by Mondy (2008) that internal recruitment methods can come from employee references, job announcements, and submissions. In contrast, according to Mondy (2008), external methods come from advertising media, agents, stock exchanges, and apprentices. So that recruitment methods can come from within and outside the company to expand the source of obtaining prospective employees so that companies have many choices. In contrast, according to Noe et al. (2010), the selection method includes interviews and a series of ability tests, personality inventory, and drug tests. In contrast, the recruitment and selection procedures are used as guidelines in its implementation so that it can run effectively and plan.

The progress of an institution cannot just happen. Of course, there are supporting factors and specific strategies owned by an agency, including what methods and procedures are used by an agency to obtain qualified employees. To be able to compare and find out what methods and procedures are used by an agency to obtain qualified employees, in this research, the researcher will examine the Samarinda State Polytechnic Vocational School, which is one of the tertiary institutions under the auspices of the Ministry of Research, Technology, and Innovation (Ristekdikti). Well-known campus in the city of Samarinda, East Kalimantan.

Samarinda State Polytechnic has many employees, and their fields of work require experts to provide good, fast, and accurate services.

The researcher's initial observations on the recruitment and selection process for contract employees at the Samarinda State Polytechnic found that many employees were recruited internally, such as family connections, relatives, and even many researchers who had graduated from the

Samarinda State Polytechnic. The procedures for carrying out recruitment and selection are very important for getting quality employees for an organization or agency, especially the Samarinda State Polytechnic.

The study aimed to determine the procedures for recruiting and selecting contract employees at the Samarinda State Polytechnic.

RESEARCH METHODS

A. Time and Place

The research was conducted from February to May 2023 at the Samarinda State Polytechnic Campus.

B. Type of Research

This qualitative descriptive research aims to provide a systematic, factual, and accurate description or explanation of the recruitment and selection procedures for contract employees at the Samarinda State Polytechnic.

C. Data Collection Techniques

Data collection techniques are a way of collecting the data needed to answer the research problem formulation (Noor, 2011) using several data collection techniques, namely interviews, observation, and literature studies (Nabuko and Achmadi, 2013; Jonathan, 2006).

D. Data Analysis Techniques

Qualitative data analysis is systematically searching for and compiling data obtained from interviews, field notes, and other materials so that it can be understood and the findings can be informed to others (Bogdan in Sugiyono, 2013). Data analysis consists of three activities simultaneously: data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion (Miles and Huberman in UlberSilalahi, 2009).

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Overview of Research Locations

Samarinda State Polytechnic, abbreviated Polnes, is a state university in Samarinda City, East Kalimantan, Indonesia. Previously named the Mulawarman University Polytechnic was officially established based on the Decree of the Directorate General of Higher Education No.080/Dikti/Kep/85 dated December 3, 1985. Polnes has a campus location on Jalan Dr. CiptoMangungkusumoSamarinda Seberang District with a land area of 10 hectares, which is equipped with a Directorate building, Lecture Room, Multipurpose Room, Laboratory and Workshop Building, Library Building, Computer Center Building, Language Center Building, Student Activities Center Building, and other supporting buildings.

The organizational structure at the Samarinda State Polytechnic consists of (1) a Director, (2) Deputy Director, (3) Units including Planning and Cooperation, Academic and Student Affairs, General Affairs and Personnel Sections, Technical Implementation Units, Centers, Department, Study Program, Lab/Workshop/Studio, (4) Educators/Lecturers, and (5) Educational Staff.

B. Recruitment Process

1. Basis of Recruitment

The basis for recruitment must be guided by the specifications of the position determined to occupy the position. In seeking the basic results of recruitment by the guidelines and job specifications, it has been carried out well, as stated by Mr. Adi Chandra S.E MM, the Head of the Personnel Sector, who said: when carrying out recruitment procedures we have guidelines as a basis for implementing these recruitment procedures, which The director makes the guideline in the form of a director's regulation. Before we recruit contract employees, we first socialize the contents of the director's regulations regarding contract employees related to their work, working period, work rules, work evaluation, and work sanctions, from light sanctions to terminating contract employees, which will be the start as a requirement in recruiting contract employees. One of the underlying reasons for the Polytechnic to recruit contract employees is a large number of Polytechnic institutions where the need for employees is urgently needed to fill existing positions according to the duties and functions of each position (Results of interview, May 16, 2023).

Furthermore, Mr. Syahrul S.H as the Personnel Staff in the Ortala field, said that our basic foundation in conducting recruitment is the director's regulations made by the director and containing procedures and procedures for implementing recruitment which will be the starting point as a requirement in recruiting contract employees (Results of interviews, May 16, 2023).

Based on the results of field interviews, it can be concluded that the Samarinda State Polytechnic has a Director's Regulation as a basis and guideline for carrying out recruitment procedures. The director's regulation also regulates job specifications which will be the initial requirements for recruiting, by Hasibuan's statement (2011) that the basis for recruitment must be guided by the job specifications that have been determined to occupy that position.

2. Recruitment Resources

The results of an interview with Mr. Syahrul S.H. as the Personnel Staff in the Ortala field show that the recruitment sources for the Samarinda State Polytechnic come from internal and external sources. For externals, recruitment notices are widely and publicly published, both from online media and print media. So those who meet the criteria are welcome to participate in this recruitment. By internal, we mean recruitment within the Samarinda State Polytechnic itself; for example, Polytechnic graduate students, we recruit them and offer them to enter as contract employees by following the stages of recruitment and selection that we make without any special treatment. (Results of the interview, May 16, 2023).

The results of interviews between researchers and contract employees regarding recruitment sources that have followed the recruitment procedure, one of which is Yunita Sintasari Sitingjak SE. MM said I knew information about recruiting contract employees through Instagram social media (Interview results, May 19, 2023). Interview with Fikriawan Mufti Haq, an Applied S1 graduate of the Samarinda State Polytechnic Majoring in Marketing Management who was placed to fill the position of Study Program Admin, Fikri said that from an internal source, namely my friends, because many of my friends have long been contracting workers at the Polytechnic Samarinda State and informed that there are still vacancies for contract workers (Results of interview, May 19, 2023).

The results of the interview above regarding the Recruitment Sources of the Samarinda State Polytechnic, it can be concluded that the Polytechnic has two sources of recruitment: internal and

external. By what was stated by Hasibuan (2011) that the source of recruitment consists of two sources, namely internal sources transferring employees who meet the standards of the positions in these vacancies, and external sources are employees who will fill positions from outside the company or agency.

3. Methods of Recruitment

The interview results with Mr. Adi Chandra S.E MM, the Head of the Personnel Division stated that the recruitment method at the Samarinda State Polytechnic was to openly follow the director's regulations and the qualifications of existing positions. For the self-selection method, we use a rating system and rank prospective employees who are fit to fill the vacant position according to the qualifications for the position (Results of interview, May 16, 2023).

From Mr. Adi Chandra's statement above, it can be stated that the Recruitment Method for the Samarinda State Polytechnic is carried out openly by the Director's Regulations, which form the basis for recruiting and selecting contract employees as stated by Hasibuan (2011) that the recruitment method has two types, namely the closed method, in which recruitment is only informed to employees or certain people. The open method, namely recruitment, is widely informing the public that there are job vacancies through electronic or print media.

4. Selection

According to Mathis & Jackson (2006), selection is the process of choosing people with the qualifications needed to fill job vacancies in an organization. Further stated by Handoko (2012), there are several indicators in the selection, including preliminary acceptance, acceptance test, and selection interview.

a. Preliminary Admission

The Polytechnic creates a special team to handle the selection process, which is called the Selection Committee; the Committee formed has SOPs with basic references written in the Director's Regulations. The scoring system and file qualifications have all been determined.

According to Handoko (2012) that the selection process is two-way. Companies choose employees, and applicants choose companies. Implementation of Preliminary Acceptance at the Samarinda State Polytechnic based on the results of an interview with Ms. Meiriza Fakhri S. Sos as a civil service staff in the General field, namely the Committee included in the announcement to prospective applicants to prepare files to be used to complete the administrative recruitment requirements. A special committee was formed to handle the selection process, Committee. The Selection Committee conducts a selection; if the file does not meet the qualifications, it will be disqualified (Interview results, May 16, 2023).

Furthermore, the interview results with Fikriawan Mufti Haq as a contract employee stated that the implementing Committee informed that those who passed the file selection had their names announced on the official Polnes website, which was informed beforehand. Coincidentally my name was there, and I was informed again to participate in the next stage (Results of interview, May 19, 2023). Handoko's statement (2012) that preliminary acceptance where the selection is two-way and the selection of incoming application letters is divided into two parts, namely, applications that meet the requirements will be called back to take the next test, while those who do not meet the requirements are declared disqualified.

b. Acceptance Test

According to Handoko (2012), the acceptance test is a process for finding prospective employee data adjusted to the required employee specifications. This acceptance test usually includes a physical test (medical test), an academic test (knowledge test), and a psychological test.

The interview results with Mr. Syahrul S. H as the staffing staff in the Oltara field regarding the acceptance test process, namely the tests carried out in the selection process, including file selection, written tests, and interviews. (Results of the interview, May 16, 2023). Samarinda State Polytechnic has implemented a three-point acceptance test. Physical tests are conducted to recruit and select prospective applicants to fill vacancies such as security. Positions by existing specifications. Whereas in the psychological test, psychologists are not used as examiners, but in interviews where interviewers are selected from people who have worked for a long time and are considered to understand in exploring the potential and motivation of prospective applicants to be used as an assessment in selection.

Furthermore, the results of YunitaSintasariSitinjau S.E M.M. interview. as a contract employee stated that there is a written test and interview for selection. While participating in the selection, there were no obstacles because the facilities provided by the Polytechnic, such as adequate writing instruments and test rooms, were sufficiently supportive. And there are no special requirements for the selection test (Results of interview, May 19, 2023).

c. Selection Interview

The interview results with Mr. Adi Chandra SE.M.M., the head of the Personnel division, stated that in conducting interviews for the selection of prospective contract employees, those responsible for the implementation are the Director and Deputy Director. (Results of the interview, May 16, 2023). Furthermore, it was stated by Mr. Syahrul S. H as the Staffing staff in the Oltara field regarding the selection interview that one of the information taken was motivation because motivation can be assessed as a person's motives. In the interview session, there are several questions to explore the motivation and potential of the applicants, and the executive Committee will also convey the rights of applicants and work qualifications and work regulations that exist at the Samarinda State Polytechnic. Prospective applicants who do not pass will be informed and welcome to take back the files so they can be used for other purposes (Results of interview, May 16, 2023).

Furthermore, the results of the interview with YunitaSintasariSitinjau SE. MM as a contract employee, stated that in the selection interview, there were several questions concerning themselves, such as work history, motivation at work, working hours, job descriptions, and income while being a contract employee, and applicants were also allowed to ask questions at the end of the interview regarding the work of contract employees at Samarinda State Polytechnic (Results of interview, May 19, 2023). Handoko's statement (2012) states that selection interviews are formal and in-depth conversations conducted to evaluate whether or not an applicant is accepted. During the selection interview for prospective contract employees, questions were asked regarding motivation, personality, and some information supporting the specifications for the position being applied for by prospective contract employees.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

Based on the description and discussion, it can be concluded as follows:

- 1 In carrying out the recruitment procedure at the Samarinda State Polytechnic already has a basis as a reference in carrying out recruitment procedures, namely the director's regulations, which contain specifications, implementation procedures, and systematic recruitment.
- 2 Samarinda State Polytechnic has two recruitment sources, Internal and External. Where the Internal itself of the Polytechnic conducts recruitment of students graduating from the Samarinda State Polytechnic, External sources are carried out openly. They are informed through print media and online media.
- 3 For the Recruitment Method, Samarinda State Polytechnic uses an open method: anyone who meets the qualifications can apply as a prospective contract employee.
4. In the Preliminary Reception, a selection of files is carried out by the Selection Committee (Selection Committee), specially made by the personnel sector. The team sorts the files of prospective applicants who will be declared passed if they meet the qualifications, while those who are not immediately declared disqualified and do not take part in the next selection stage.
5. The selection tests carried out are preliminary tests or file selection, then there are academic tests to determine the abilities and insights of prospective applicants, as well as an interview test as the final stage and evaluation in making the selection.
6. Competent people conduct the selection interviews to gather information, potential, and motivation of prospective contract employees to serve as assessment and evaluation material for the selection committee.

B. Suggestion

1. It is hoped that the Samarinda State Polytechnic will maintain recruitment according to specifications using an open method so that there will be more prospective contract employee applicants.
2. Continue to conduct the selection process for prospective employees recruited internally or externally without any special treatment.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Alwi, Hasan, et al. 2003. Big Indonesian Dictionary. Library Center, Jakarta.
- Ambar, T. S. 2003. Human Resource Management Concept Theory and Development in the Context of Public Organizations. Science Graha, Yogyakarta..
- Ambar, T. S. &Rosidah. 2009. Human Resource Management. Science Graha, Yogyakarta.
- Ardiyos. 2008. Big Dictionary of Accounting. Citra Hatra Prima, Jakarta.
- Baiq, S. 2013. Human Resource Studies in the Labor Recruitment Process in Companies. Widya Scientific Journal, 40.
- Burhanuddin, Y. 2015. Human Resource Management in Islamic Financial Institutions. Raja GrafindoPersada, Jakarta.
- Djoko, H. 2010. HR Strategy in Facing Global Competition.
- Donni, J. P. 2014. HR Planning and Development. Alfabeta, Bandung.
- Handoko, T. 2012. Personnel Management & Human Resources (Second Edition ed.). BPF, Yogyakarta.
- Hasibuan, M. S. 2012. Human Resource Management. Earth Script, Jakarta.
- Lexy, J. M. 2004. Qualitative Research Methodology. Roskarya, Bandung
- Marwansyah. 2012. Human Resource Management. Alfabeta, Bandung.
- Mathis, Robert L., & Jackson. 2006. Human Resource Management. SalembaEmpat, Jakarta.
- Miles, Matthew and Huberman, A Michael. 2014. Qualitative Data Analysis. Indonesian Press University, Jakarta.
- Nawawi, H. 2003. Human Resource Management. Gajah Mada Press, Yogyakarta.
- Pahlevi, R. 2013. Analysis of the Effectiveness of the Recruitment and Selection Process in Meeting the Needs of Human Resources. 72